

Electronic Supplementary Material:

Cribellate thread production as model for spider's spinneret kinematics

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ESM_1 Ventral view on the spinneret movements of an anaesthetised *Badumna longinqua*, 4x slowed down

ESM_2 Lateral view on the spinneret movements of an anaesthetised *Badumna longinqua*

ESM_3 Ventro-lateral view on the spinning process of *Badumna longinqua* during cribellate thread production, 4x slowed down

ESM_4 Spinning apparatus of *Badumna longinqua* (a) A pair of anterior (AS) and posterior spinnerets (PS) and a pseudo-divided cribellum (Cr) are clearly visible (b) Median spinnerets (MS) were visible after removal of the AS; SEM images; Scale bars (a), (b) 300 µm